

Study of the Category of Communicative Purpose in Linguistics

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Abstract: This article analyzes the study of the category of communicative purpose in linguistics, in particular, how it is expressed in the Arabic and Uzbek languages. Communicative purpose is one of the main tasks of language, which ensures the mutual communication of speakers through purposeful expression in the speech process. The methods of expression of the communicative purpose in the Arabic and Uzbek languages show specific differences in language structures. The article analyzes how the communicative purpose is implemented in these languages through speech forms, structural features and linguistic means.

Keywords: Communicative purpose, linguistics, Arabic language, Uzbek language, dialogue, speech, semantics, pragmatics, language and culture, linguistics.

Introduction: Communicative purpose is one of the main tasks of speech, which serves to organize communication between speakers, convey certain information, or satisfy some other need. Each word and phrase in a language is intended to achieve a communicative purpose. In speech science, communicative purpose is an important direction in the study of the pragmatic aspect of language. The implementation of non-verbal communication, its effectiveness, and the specific characteristics of communication are related to the linguistic foundations of each language. Arabic and Uzbek languages have different linguistic systems, which have different features of the structure and lexicon of the language in expressing their communicative purposes. This article analyzes the study of communicative purpose and its linguistic means in Arabic and Uzbek languages.

Main part: Communicative purpose is the expression of the goals and needs of speakers using language tools in linguistics. Lexical, syntactic, and pragmatic means are used to implement communicative goals in speech. Types of communicative goals, how they are transformed, and the means used to transform them are a separate branch of linguistics. Pragmatic aspects of language play a key role in studying the category of communicative purpose.

Arabic language and communicative purpose: The Arabic language, with its rich vocabulary, traditional expressions, and phraseologisms, requires special approaches to expressing communicative goals. Structural means such as reporting, requesting, proposing, and refusing are often used to achieve communicative goals in Arabic. Using examples, how communicative goals are implemented in Arabic and their semantic features are analyzed. Language tools in Arabic, including word combinations and syntactic structures, provide various forms of communicative goals. Arabic language mainly uses extended syntactic structures, complex expressions and phraseological units. To achieve the goal of speech, language is often used that provides additional information about time, place or tense. In Arabic, communicative goals are expressed more clearly and completely based on numerous phraseological expressions and certain cultural and religious contexts. For example, when expressing communicative goals such as proposals, permission or refusal, Arabic expressions are based on certain cultural and moral values.

Uzbek language and communicative goal: In Uzbek, communicative goals are mainly realized through simple and complex sentences, statements, demands and requests. In Uzbek, syntactic means, lexical units and traditional expressions are widely used to realize communicative goals. In Uzbek, like Arabic,

there are phraseological units and word combinations that express many communicative goals. In the Uzbek language, simple and complex structures are used together in modern language to express communicative goals. In the Uzbek language, more simple and straightforward syntactic structures are used to express communicative goals. The syntax, phraseology and lexical means of the Uzbek language are effective tools for conveying clear and accurate information in communication. In expressing communicative goals in the Uzbek language, the goal is achieved using more word combinations, short phrases and simple sentences. Also, compared to perfectly structured phrases in the Arabic language, more direct and simple words are used in the Uzbek language, which allows for quick and effective communication. By comparing the methods of expressing communicative goals in the Arabic and Uzbek languages, it is possible to determine their structural and semantic features. Phraseological units, syntactic structures and lexical means associated with communicative goals in the Arabic and Uzbek languages are different from each other. However, there are similar approaches to achieving communicative goals in both languages. For example, common communicative goals such as providing information, requests, and suggestions are present in both Arabic and Uzbek.

Results and discussion: There are some similarities and differences in linguistics in the expression of communicative goals in Arabic and Uzbek. In both languages, complex syntactic and lexical means are used to achieve a specific goal in communication. While Arabic uses more complex and multi-layered syntactic structures, in Uzbek clear and simple expressions are more common. However, in both languages, the main task of the communicative goal is the effective implementation of communication. The analyzed materials also showed how communicative goals are implemented in speech in both languages and how language tools are used in the communication process.

The main differences between the Arabic and Uzbek languages in the expression of communicative goals are visible in the level of complexity of syntactic structures and lexical means. In Arabic, more complex structures and multi-layered phraseological units are used to express communicative goals. In Uzbek, simple and direct expressions of communicative goals are more common. However, both languages show similar approaches to ensuring clear and effective communication in certain social situations.

The study of the category of communicative purpose in Arabic and Uzbek will greatly contribute to the effective organization of the communication process in linguistics. In both languages, various language tools are used to achieve communicative goals, but the methods and structure of their use differ. In Arabic, the communicative goal is expressed through more complex and extended syntactic structures, while in Uzbek, clear and simple structures are preferred. However, both languages use all the possibilities of the language to ensure effectiveness in communication.

Conclusion: According to the results of the article, the study of communicative goals in Arabic and Uzbek is of great importance in linguistics. Although the means and methods of expressing communicative goals in these languages differ, their common goal is to effectively organize the communication process. In Arabic and Uzbek, language structures and lexical means play a special role in expressing communicative goals. The study of communicative goals allows for a deeper understanding of the pragmatic aspects of the language, which in turn helps to learn the language more effectively and improve its functions in communication.

Also, communicative goals in both languages are based on different cultural, social and linguistic contexts. This increases their importance in language teaching, translation and ensuring compatibility in communication. A deeper understanding of the similarities and differences between communicative goals in Arabic and Uzbek allows linguists to study the pragmatic and semantic aspects of the language more broadly.

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